

HUFI STUDENTS' PERCEPTION OF A GOOD BALANCE OF ENGLISH COMMUNICATION SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

In the age of globalization and integration, English is becoming more and more important than it has ever been. Undoubtedly, it has become the language of international communication which facilitates development and co-operation in all fields, especially in business. Consequently, English is the most important soft skill for a job seeker in Viet Nam, nowadays. This reality urges the improvement of the learning and teaching of English in order that the students can be best equipped with this mean of communication before they can join the workforce. Traditionally, all English 4 communicative skills are equally emphasized in classrooms. In Hufi, there is no exception. However, at workplace the frequency of use and the role of these 4 skills are different. Furthermore, time located for English teaching has been cut greatly. As a result, a right emphasis on each specific skill both in learning and teaching English is necessary to enhance learning result of the students and to better prepare them for the workplace. Very few researches have ever addressed this issue which involves enormous effort of not only teachers, students but also employers. Due to the limited time and scope of this paper, the researcher only tries to explore the importance of 4 English communicative skills from the perspectives of Hufi non-major students and compare with the opinions of employers. The results of this study is believed to provide Hufi English teachers and students an insight about the demand for each skill at workplace, which will help the teaching and learning stay more focused to better meet the language needs at work.

Key words: English communicative skills, workplace, language demand

1 INTRODUCTION

No one can deny the truth that English is an international language of culture, business, science and technology nowadays. The importance of English in global communication demands the necessity of English communication skills for operating a business worldwide. In developing countries like Vietnam a strong command of English is necessary than ever as the country is making an effort to integrate into the world community. The ability to comprehend, to speak, write in English clearly is a necessary requirement for job seekers as many foreign companies have flocked to Viet Nam to do business after the implementation of open door policy.

To fulfill the demand of the country and to satisfy the needs of the students, Hochiminh University of Food Industry (hereafter abbreviated as Hufi) has constantly upgraded the teaching

and learning facilities, teaching methods. Numerous revisions which place more emphasis on the communicative competence of the language in the teaching syllabus have also been made. However, due to limited class time and students' English knowledge, the results achieved have been modest. To better prepare students for the workplace and to make most of the teaching program, it is suggested that the teaching syllabus should be more focused on the language sectors students need. Then, a major problem arises that is what language sectors should be emphasized more? Should 4 English communicative skills are equally taught in class? This research, thus, was done to address these questions.

To find out the gap between the current teaching syllabus and students' perception of their needs to different language skills, the following research questions help the study go:

What is Hufi students' perception of the role of English?

What is Hufi students' perception of the current teaching curriculum?

What is Hufi students' perception of a good balance of 4 communicative skill?

2 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Due to limited time and scope of this paper, the researcher only made an effort to analyze the needs of English learning based on students' perceptions. A questionnaire was administered to 178 students including 95 males and 83 females who were taking their A2 course at Hufi. It focused on their expectation of the percentage of 4 communicative skills they wish to improve in Hufi English courses. The majority of them (63) started learning English when they were at junior high school. A big number (34%) even learnt English at primary school. Only a very small percentage (3%) has been learning English for 3 years. This means most of the students who took part in the survey had a lot English learning experience. They had good understanding of the language and they know clearly what they lack and need to expect from the course at Hufi.

A questionnaire was adopted to explore the participants' perspectives and needs. It comprised three sections: The first section focused on the participants' personal information, the second section focused on their English proficiency levels, and the final section focused on their needs of English skills. The data collected from the questionnaire were used to understand the differences between the students' course learning content and their expectations for language skill improvement.

3 LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1 Needs analysis

Many researchers have emphasized the vital role of needs analysis in English teaching and course design. Needs analysis can facilitate the learning effectiveness because that help learners can learn what they want. Needs analysis can help learners determine "what they may know, what they can do, and what they need to learn". Most important, it helps learners maximize language learning and skills to meet their real needs.

To sum up, needs analysis involves seeking and clarifying information about learners' needs in an English course.

3.2 Previous research

In an effort to determine students' needs for language courses, Kaur and Khan, conducted a needs analysis of English for art and design students in Malaysia, found that students perceived English speaking as the most important communicative skill in their courses and their careers, followed by English listening, reading, and writing skills.

Tseng also confirmed in his research that learning speaking skills was particularly necessary in Asia. A sample of 83 undergraduate students majoring in the arts participated in his study. The results showed that the two main language skills in need were conversation and writing. In addition to the compulsory courses, students wanted to be trained in speaking and listening skills. They wanted to acquire speaking and listening skills for daily life. Furthermore, reading skills are also necessary for understanding specific website content.

Although the above researches have contributed greatly to the insight of language teaching, the research subjects together with their own learning and teaching condition make needs analysis is necessary in every setting. Further more, it is important that English language course providers understand the expectations of learners when designing or reviewing course syllabi. Therefore, a research into students' perception of a good balance of English communicative skills in Hufi is needed.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Question 1 and 2 aim to explore students' view of the role of English. Unsurprisingly, all most all of the informants' answers indicate a strong need to learn English for their future job. In respond to question 1, 95% (169/178) of the students said they wanted to learn English for their future job. This result is in line with the finding of question 2 which shows that 162 out of 178 respondents (91%) thought that English is important or very important in their future job. The students' responses to the first two questions reveal their strong demand to learn English for communication at workplace.

Answers to question 3 help to elaborate students' perception of the language areas they wish to improve. The result is, again, not surprising. The surveyed students would like to learn English for their future job. Consequently, 4 communicative skills were selected by majority of them as the language sector they wanted to learn most. This further confirms their awareness of the vital role of English in their success in their future career. However, their opinions of the emphasis of these skills in the school syllabus reveal that their needs to improve these language skills are different when a dominant number agreed or strongly agreed that they should not have the same weight in the syllabus.

Communication in real life requires integrated skills. Therefore, question 5 was designed with pairs of skills in order to find out which one, students need to develop most. Of the four language skills, more than half (55%, 98/178) of the students perceived that their speaking and listening

skills required the most improvement. This is understandable because for most language learners, knowing a language is equated with speaking that language fluently. Listening is no less important as English has become the global language that means a good communicator must be able to comprehend different accents from parts of the world. However, a very large number of students (49%, 87/178) also opted for Speaking and Reading when they answered this question. A possible explanation is that nowadays, most job candidates need to do an IQ test or a reading test to prove that they are eligible enough for an interview which will be conducted orally. This very true fact requires learners not only excellent speaking ability but reading competence as well. As most Hufi students wish to master English so that they can be able to enter the modern workforces, a strong demand for speaking, listening and reading is unarguable.

In replying to the last question, most of students (91%) asserted that they are taught all the macro as well as micro skills in their class while a small number did not select sub-skills as the content learning during class time. This significant difference may be attributed to students' unequal level of English knowledge. In some classes, teachers may skip teaching vocabulary and grammar because their learners were good at these two areas. However, the respondents' opinions to question 5 also indicate that students do not always learn the skills that they need in their English course at Hufi. In other words, the students' perceptions and the current syllabus toward communicative skills were mismatched. Therefore, teaching the skills that students expect to acquire is crucial to promote their learning motivation and, at the same time, enhance the learning and teaching results at Hufi.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The purpose of this study is to analyze the learning needs of English communicative skills as perceived by students. Our results reveal discrepancies between what is taught at school and the requirements of the learners. Although a great strike has been made to the learning and teaching of English in Hufi, further improvement is still needed as most students do not feel satisfied with the current syllabus. While all language elements have the same weight in the syllabus, students would prefer to improve certain abilities, namely speaking, listening and writing as they want to be better prepared for their future occupation. The findings of this research suggest that a shift toward more specific focus on certain language skills is needed urgently to meet the expectation of Hufi students. A more realistic and adequate syllabus for English learners at Hufi will certainly improve their English abilities. What also deserve attention is a more career-oriented course should be designed to help them transition successfully to their future careers after graduation. Last but not least, the test should also exclude sub – skills and assess only communicative skills with different weight decided by Hufi students' learning needs. A focus on the major needs of learners, undoubtedly, will enhance their learning motivation and their learning results accordingly.

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APPENDIX

QUESTIONNAIRE TO THE STUDENTS

This questionnaire is designed to explore Hufi students' perception of the balance of 4 communicative skills in the syllabus. The collected information will be used in a research.

Please read all the questions carefully and circle the appropriate choice or choices.

Thank you very much for your cooperation.

Part I: ABOUT YOU

Age:

Gender: a. Male b. Female

3. You have learned English since you were in

- | | |
|----------------------------|----------------------------------|
| a. University | b. Senior secondary school |
| c. Junior secondary school | d. Others (Please specify) |

Part II: RESEARCH QUESTION

1. Why do you learn English?

- | | |
|---------------------------------------|------------------------------------|
| a. Because it is a compulsory subject | b. To read professional literature |
| c. For my future job | d. Others |

2. How important is English for your future job?

- | | |
|-----------------------|------------------|
| a. Very important | b. Important |
| c. Not very important | d. Not important |

3. In this English course, I most want to improve my.....

- a. 4 communicative skills
- b. Sub – skills: Grammar & Vocabulary – Terminology
- c. Others

4. In my opinion, the English course at Hufi should focus equally on all 4 communicative skills

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Uncertain
- d. Disagree
- e. Strongly disagree

5. 2 communicative skills I want to improve most are.... (you have 2 choices)

- a. Listening & Speaking
- b. Listening & Writing
- c. Listening & Reading
- d. Speaking & Writing
- e. Speaking & Reading
- f. Writing & Reading

6. In your current class, your lessons focus on (you can have more than one choice)

- a. Listening
- b. Speaking
- c. Writing
- d. Reading
- e. Grammar
- f. Vocabulary